

PRIORITY AREAS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF QUALIFIED PERSONNEL COMPETENCIES FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH AND EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT

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***Abstract.** The rapidly changing modern economy puts forward new requirements for the personnel qualifications and competencies. The article discusses the main priority areas for the development of qualified personnel competencies to ensure sustainable economic growth and effective management. The key competencies are outlined, including leadership, communication, decision-making, innovation, teamwork and result orientation. A model of competencies covering three levels is proposed: basic (knowledge), operational (skills) and strategic (values and attitudes). The key methods for training and development of competencies are identified.*

***Keywords:** management competencies, sustainable development, competency-based approach, leadership, communication, motivation, innovation, decision-making.*

Introduction

In today's world, characterized by rapid socio-economic, scientific and technological changes, the need to develop a personality capable of adaptation, creative thinking and innovation comes to the fore. Such a personality is an important element in ensuring efficient management and promoting sustainable economic growth, as it is the driving force behind transformations in the modern world.

Sustainable economic development is based on the development of competencies that allow not only responding to challenges but also creating new opportunities for growth. Effective management requires the ability to think strategically, innovate and continuously improve, which directly depends on the level of professional training of qualified personnel and their ability to implement changes. Increasing requirements for staff competence, professional qualification level and adaptability contribute to the formation of the basis for stable economic development and improved management efficiency at all levels of government agencies, organizations and enterprises.

Some researchers believe that "competence is a set of interrelated human qualities (knowledge, skills, abilities) that are necessary for effective work in a particular field, and competence is the ability to possess these competencies, including personal attitude to the object of activity"[1]. It should be added that competence is not only about possessing competencies, but also about the ability to practically apply them in everyday activities. The author proposes to consider competencies at three levels: understanding, activity and being [1]. The first level, "understanding," includes the basic set of knowledge necessary for

professional activity; the second level, "activity," is the ability to apply this knowledge in practice; the third level, "being," covers the system of professional and human values, as well as the ability to coexist harmoniously in society. Thus, competence can be viewed as a characteristic of a personality that allows him or her to solve problems and make decisions in a particular field.

The competency-based approach to the development of skilled personnel is a modern methodology aimed at developing not only professional knowledge but also a wide range of competencies that allow employees to work effectively in a constantly changing environment. This approach emphasizes the importance of developing the abilities, skills and attitudes necessary for sustainable economic growth and effective management.

The analysis of competencies characteristics and their structure identifies three levels at which competence is formed (Fig. 1). Each level of employee competence formation affects the other. For example, the personal level affects the cognitive and activity levels, because the employee's attitude to the activity will determine the level of knowledge and the way they obtain it, which in turn will affect the dynamics of competence development [2].

Fig.1. Levels of competence development [2].

In our opinion, the uniqueness of the competency-based approach to the development of skilled personnel for sustainable economic growth and effective management lies in its systemic approach focused on the development of not only professional knowledge but also critical practical skills. This approach differs from traditional methods in the following important aspects:

1. Focus on market needs:

- the competency-based approach ensures that skills are constantly updated according to changes in the labor market. It facilitates a rapid response to new economic challenges, including digitalization, globalization, environmental challenges and new business models.
- sustainable economic development requires not only preservation of existing knowledge, but also the ability to quickly adapt to new conditions, introduce innovations and work with the latest technologies.

2. Integration of professional skills: the unique approach is to combine technical competencies (hard skills) with social, communication, creative and leadership skills (soft skills). This harmonious integration helps employees not only to perform tasks efficiently, but also to cooperate effectively in teams, solve problems and initiate changes.

3. Focus on sustainable development and long-term goals: the competency-based approach considers the importance of sustainable economic growth by training personnel who understand long-term development strategies, environmental responsibility, efficient resource management, and the implementation of sustainable production principles. This allows to combine economic needs with social and environmental goals.

4. Continuous process of learning and self-improvement:

- this approach emphasizes continuous learning and development throughout life (life-long learning). This allows employees to be prepared for new challenges and take advantage of opportunities that arise in the labor market.

- continuous improvement of competencies allows to maintain a high level of competitiveness of both employees and enterprises in the global environment.

5. Comprehensive approach to management and leadership: the competency-based approach prepares personnel not only to perform specific professional tasks but also to make management decisions at the strategic level. It ensures the development of the ability to effectively manage organizations, which is essential for successful business in a challenging economic environment.

6. Implementation of innovations and technological changes: the modern labor market is actively changing due to technological innovations, and the competency-based approach ensures the training of personnel capable of not only responding to these changes, but also initiating them. This is especially important for ensuring effective management and sustainable growth in innovation-oriented economies.

Such a system promotes the integration of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and personal qualities, making future personnel competitive, flexible and ready to innovate.

To apply the competency-based approach, it is important to have a clearly defined classification of competencies [3]. D. McClelland, M. Dalziel, R. Page offer the following list of competency's types: 1) theoretical and professional knowledge; 2) job skills and universal skills (communication, management, etc.); 3) ability to master new activities; 4) value orientations and characteristics of motivation; 5) personal traits and psychophysiological characteristics [4].

Study [5] offers a model that provides a simple presentation of the direct and positive relationship between the identified managerial competencies and the main pillars of sustainable development. The authors found that there is a direct positive relationship between competencies in communication, leadership, development orientation, achievement orientation, motivation, teamwork, innovation and decision-making, economic viability, social inclusion and environmental protection.

In our opinion, important areas for developing the competencies of qualified personnel for sustainable economic growth and effective management are the following:

1. Professional (technical) competencies: this is a basic element of successful professional activity. Without proper knowledge and skills in a particular field, an employee will not be able to perform tasks at a high level. Professional competencies help to increase production efficiency, improve the quality of products and services, which directly affects the competitiveness and sustainable economic growth of the organization and the state.

2. Managerial competencies: effective management of resources, people and processes is key to ensuring growth and sustainable development. Managers with these competencies are capable to plan strategies, optimize processes and make rational decisions. This helps to increase productivity, minimize costs and achieve long-term goals.

3. Digital competencies: given the rapid digitalization of the economy, employees with advanced digital skills can adapt to new working conditions and use the latest technologies to increase productivity. The introduction of digital tools allows automating processes, increasing efficiency, and providing access to global markets. This is critical for economic growth in the digital economy.

4. Innovative and creative competencies: innovation and creativity are the drivers of development. A workforce that is capable to generate new ideas and solutions helps businesses stay competitive, introduce new products and services, and optimize internal processes. This stimulates economic growth and the development of new markets.

5. Communication competencies: effective communication is the basis for successful interaction within the organization and with external partners. It helps to understand customer needs better, establish cooperation, resolve conflicts, and make quick decisions. This contributes to effective management and ensures sustainable development.

6. Social and ethical competencies: nowadays, when attention to social and environmental aspects is constantly growing, having ethical and social competencies helps organizations to adhere to high standards of responsibility. This strengthens reputation, increases trust from customers and society, which contributes to sustainable long-term development.

7. Analytical and strategic competencies: the ability to analyze data and strategic planning makes it possible to respond to market changes in a timely manner, predict risks and identify promising areas of development. This helps to reduce uncertainty and ensure sustainable development of the enterprise, which, in turn, contributes to stable economic growth.

8. Adaptability and resilience competencies: the modern labor market requires employees to be flexible and able to respond quickly to changes. In the face of global challenges and crises (such as pandemics or war), adaptability and resilience competencies allow organizations not only to survive but also to develop. This is the key to long-term stability and development in a changing environment.

These areas cover not only professional knowledge but are also crucial for sustainable economic growth and effective management. They allow organizations and institutions not only to carry out their activities effectively, but also to be prepared for the challenges of the modern world, to innovate, optimize processes and ensure long-term success.

Today, higher education institutions play a key role in shaping the competencies needed for sustainable economic growth and effective governance. They not only provide basic knowledge in various fields, but also contribute to the development of important skills such as critical thinking, leadership, innovation, teamwork, and decision-making. Through the integration of practical tasks, project activities, and research, universities develop students' ability to adapt to rapid changes in the business environment and successfully implement sustainable development strategies.

This is confirmed by the study of the authors [6], who point out that participants from different areas within the university, as well as external individuals and organizations, can come together to jointly address real-world sustainability challenges. Their Living Lab model

is a dynamic network that connects the intellectual and other resources of an institution with practical sustainability challenges on or off campus. It effectively breaks down the boundaries between traditionally separated activities in education, research, external engagement, operations, and administration. It also allows the professional sustainability team on campus to enter into a closer dialogue with faculty and students to address real-world issues through experiential learning and teaching and/or research projects implemented both within the university and with external partners.

Competencies, such as knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes, help to create a sustainable management system that is focused on long-term economic growth and efficiency. They allow not only to respond to changes but also to anticipate them, using innovative solutions and approaches that ensure sustainable development. We propose a model of competencies for achieving sustainable economic growth and effective management (Fig.2).

The development of these competencies will allow future professionals to effectively implement solutions aimed at sustainable economic development, while contributing to the improvement of management efficiency. A balanced combination of professional knowledge, innovation, leadership, social responsibility, and digital competencies will create the basis for the long-term competitiveness and sustainability of organizations and the economy as a whole.

To optimize the functioning of competencies, it is important to develop them comprehensively. This includes continuous training, development of leadership skills and analytical abilities, as well as the formation of ethical responsibility for decisions (Tab.1).

Fig. 2. Competency model for achieving sustainable economic growth and effective management.

Table 1. Key methods for training and competence development

	Specifications	Advantages	Illustration
1. Trainings and seminars	Practical classes with a focus on developing specific skills (communication, leadership, decision-making).	Ensure active participation, exchange of experience and feedback from experts.	Training in emotional intelligence, strategic planning or project management to improve management skills.
2. Coaching and mentoring	Individual approach, which provides support from an experienced specialist (mentor or coach) to develop competencies through consultations and recommendations.	Focus on personal and professional development through individual assignments, case studies and personalized learning strategies.	Coaching on leadership or decision-making, mentoring on implementing innovations in work processes.
3. Simulations and scenario modeling	Use of realistic models and simulations to develop competencies in conditions that simulate real-life situations.	It provides an opportunity to test and improve skills without risk, allowing employees to explore different solutions in difficult conditions.	Crisis management or strategic decision-making simulations.
4. Case-methods	Analyzing real or fictional business cases to develop analytical thinking, problem-oriented approaches and collective problem solving.	Allows to practice decision-making skills in real-life situations, analyze and solve problems that arise in professional activities.	Case studies on change management or innovation.
5. Team building and group work	Activities that promote teamwork, trust and interaction in groups.	Improves communication skills and the ability to work in a team, develops cooperation and joint problem solving.	Team building activities or working together on projects in interdisciplinary groups.

These methods can be adapted to the specifics of an organization or industry, and their combined use will ensure the comprehensive development of competencies necessary for sustainable economic growth and effective management.

Conclusions. The development of qualified personnel key competencies is an important factor in ensuring sustainable economic growth and effective management. Changes in

educational programs, emphasis on priority skills, and the introduction of innovative approaches will form the basis for building a human resource capacity which is able to successfully respond to the modern challenges. Ensuring sustainable economic growth requires professionals to have knowledge in the field of sustainable development, covering environmental, social and economic aspects. These competencies are becoming critical to preserving natural resources and ensuring social responsibility of business. In the context of global competition, there is a growing demand for innovative and entrepreneurial competencies. Educational programs should stimulate creative thinking and readiness to implement startups, new technologies and products that meet the requirements of the times.

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